

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A MODERN TOOL FOR TRANSFORMING HIGHER EDUCATION

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Аннотация. Ушбу илмий мақолада сунъий интеллект – олий таълимни трансформация қилишнинг замонавий технологияси сифатида жорий қилиш масалалари тадқиқ этилган бўлиб, шунингдек, олий таълимни ривожлантиришида сунъий интеллектдан фойдаланишнинг истиқболли йўналишлари таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: олий таълим, сунъий интеллект, рақамли трансформация, стратегия, кадрларни тайёрлаш, тўртинчи саноат инқилоби, Саноат 4.0.

Аннотация. В данной научной статье исследуются вопросы внедрения искусственного интеллекта как современной технологии трансформации высшего образования, а также перспективные направления использования искусственного интеллекта в развитии высшего образования.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, искусственный интеллект, цифровая трансформация, стратегия, подготовка кадров, четвертая промышленная революция, Индустрия 4.0.

Abstract. This scientific article explores the issues of introduction of artificial intelligence as a modern technology for the transformation of higher education, as well as the prospective directions of using artificial intelligence in the development of higher education.

Keywords: higher education, artificial intelligence, digital transformation, strategy, training, fourth industrial revolution, industry 4.0.

In recent decades, domestic higher education has been in a state of constant transformation caused by the need to integrate into the global educational space, improve the quality of educational services provided, increase the competitiveness of Uzbek universities in the international arena, as well as general socio-economic changes that have occurred in the country.

Modern education is being transformed into a mobile and open system. The introduction of information and communication technologies and electronic educational resources into the educational process has contributed to the formation of a new educational paradigm [1].

The essence of digital transformation of education is expressed in the achievement of the necessary educational results by each student through the personalization of the educational process based on the use of the growing potential of digital technologies, including the use of artificial intelligence methods, virtual reality tools; development of a digital educational environment in educational institutions; provision of publicly available broadband access to the Internet, work with big data [2].

The term "Artificial Intelligence" (AI) was introduced by American computer scientist John McCarthy in 1956. Artificial intelligence (AI) is the ability of intelligent systems and algorithms to perform creative functions traditionally performed by humans. The key task of AI is the intelligent modeling of achievable cognitive processes.

Humanity is on the threshold of the fourth industrial revolution [3], it is already impossible to prevent the development of artificial intelligence. Neural networks solve a number

of problems many times more efficiently and accurately than humans, which makes the complete automation of a large number of jobs in the near future [4], and therefore will lead to an increase in unemployment. At the same time, it should be noted that at different times, various technologies contributed to the displacement of people from the labor market, but humans have always managed to adapt to the changes taking place. Given all the benefits of using AI, including increased labor productivity, humans need to complement it [5], and not be dependent on it.

AI technologies determine the development of the global economy today. Investments in them constitute the main investments of venture capital in the United States. A similar boom is taking place in Europe, Japan, and China [6]. According to international experts, investments in artificial intelligence technologies have tripled from 2014 to 2017 and amounted to about \$40 billion. In 2018, the global market for technological solutions developed on the basis of artificial intelligence amounted to \$21.5 billion and, according to expert forecasts, will reach almost \$140 billion by 2024. It is expected that due to the introduction of technological solutions developed on the basis of artificial intelligence in various sectors of the economy and areas of public relations, the growth of the world economy in 2024 will amount to at least \$1 trillion [7].

Artificial intelligence technologies can be applied in a wide variety of industries and spheres: industry, construction, transport, communications, education, science, healthcare, finance, trade, culture, tourism, housing and communal services, etc.

The use of AI can lead to significant changes in the field of education, creating new opportunities to restructure the work of the entire industry. The introduction of AI technologies in the field of education will increase the efficiency of the educational process, the resources spent on its organization.

The artificial intelligence system of the educational process should include the following elements [8]:

- a search information system that ensures the formation of a database of the educational process from various sources;
- an automatically updated library of electronic textbooks, manuals and methodological instructions;
- a system for monitoring the level of knowledge of students, including a subsystem for continuous monitoring of their academic performance, activity and results;
- a library of test assignments that is automatically adjusted to the level of preparation of each student depending on his or her results;
- an automated system for creating a schedule and distributing the academic workload;
- a service system that ensures communication between the student and the educational organization.

The use of AI technologies in education can play a significant role in human learning and development throughout life.

The following can be highlighted as advanced technologies of Industry 4.0 in the content and means of modern education [9]:

- Internet of Things (remote access educational laboratories; remote laboratory stands);
- Additive manufacturing (3D printers in educational workshops; 3D modeling (in the disciplines of computer science, mathematics); manufacturing of robot parts, technical devices in additional education of students);

- AI, machine learning and robotics (use of avatars and chatbots in the educational process for consulting, testing and designing individual educational routes for students; use of presence robots in distance learning);
- Big data, block chain and cloud computing (formation of secure portfolios of students and teachers; recording the formation of educational and professional competencies; use of cloud technologies in the educational process);
- Virtual and augmented reality (use of simulation laboratory stands and laboratory installations with elements of augmented reality in the educational process).

Universities are not only the bearers of academic tradition and system-wide efficiency, but also have incredible potential for innovation and non-standard initiatives. Only by realizing this truth can we realize the potential for transformation that exists in the higher education system [10]. The use of AI technologies by universities facilitates the process of providing educational services and helps improve their quality. AI allows us to create an individual educational trajectory for each student for successful study at the university and further professional growth.

Fig. 1. Promising areas of use of artificial intelligence in the field of higher education

It should be noted that promising areas of use of artificial intelligence in the field of higher education are not limited to those listed above.

In our opinion, AI is not a competitor to the teaching staff either in teaching or in assessing students' knowledge. AI is an auxiliary but valuable tool that can perform and improve a large number of different operations carried out at the university, help in organizing an effective educational process and building the necessary communications.

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